

IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH

Shadmanbekova K.

Tashkent State University of Economics,
TIF, senior teacher of "Foreign languages" department
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Abstract; English is one of the official languages in the world. Learning English helps to achieve success in every career stage or daily life. In this thesis is discussed about importance of learning foreign languages.

Key words; English, language, career, foreign language, ability

Of course, everyone has known that knowledge of English can be very useful in life. Firstly, to know English, we can get more information from various media. This may be your computer, where all the technical information is written in English. You can read books in the original language; the translation does not always objectively reflect the true feelings and emotions that the author put into the novel. What about technical literature? After all, in this case, you could independently study any technique, program and equipment that interests you. Secondly, if you know English, you will always have the opportunity to talk with interesting people on a wide variety of topics, and besides, you can always travel abroad as a tourist, which is much more convenient and cheaper. Do you want to build your career? In this case, you need English like a fresh air. You dream is being an international businessman. What do you think, can you do it without any foreign languages, especially English? Of course, to build up your business career, all international negotiations, trading on stock exchanges - they are all conducted in foreign languages, and you want to take part in international conferences, communicate with business people, read international magazines and newspapers about business. in this case, you must know English language, improving it every day.

Foreign language skills are a necessary element in the education of successful people. Nowadays, this item is presented in the questionnaires of personnel departments of public and private organizations. Candidates who, in addition to their native language, know at least one more, make favorable impression on employers. At present, the personal and professional development of a modern person cannot do without foreign languages. The ability to negotiate with representatives of different cultures forms the development of horizons and allows you to have the opportunity to climb the career ladder in the company, makes it possible to make useful contacts. The changes that have taken place in the past decades have made it possible to open

borders for active interaction with other countries, while allowing the exchange of resources and achievements between them. For the successful development of both a particular person and various companies, it became necessary to have contacts with representatives of other countries. In the process of integration into the global economic and cultural space, with the increase and high-quality change in world standards, knowledge of foreign languages becomes one of the important tasks of modern person. A foreign language allows you to open the possibility for free communication and interaction between people of different nationalities and cultures.

At the moment, good knowledge of any foreign language is a privilege, a skill necessary for a successful life. Knowledge of foreign languages is now one of the main fundamental elements that shape the life of a successful person. A foreign language is required not only in order to purposefully interact in economics and politics, culture and literature, but also for the development of a person as a whole. The fundamental moment in the study of a foreign language is the need to understand and comprehend the worldview of another country, having explored its culture in the language of this country, to get the opportunity to communicate with people of a different mentality and a chance to acquire new knowledge in different fields of knowledge. The degree of proficiency in foreign languages is especially important for all young people who want to have a chance to get a well-paid job in the future, this will allow them to be able to touch the outside world, improve their own communication skills. In accordance with the study, confident knowledge of foreign languages helps to realize oneself in the future, teaches tolerance and trains memory, and is also one of the most important components in their employment. Knowledge of one foreign language allows you to have increased chances for successful employment today. It is important for the employer to understand how useful the employee to whom he provides the workplace can be. A foreign language in this case is not only an ability inherent in a person, but also a condition for the successful interaction of a company and its development within it.

In a broad sense, communication in foreign language is the basic ability to communicate in the native language of another country. It is the possibility of mutual understanding of foreigners and the expression of their thoughts to them, the definition of concepts, thoughts, the transfer of facts and opinions. Communication with people in foreign languages requires the presence of such qualities as patience and intercultural understanding. Particular importance is

cultural diversity, as well as interest and curiosity in relation to languages and intercultural interaction.

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